
OPEN ENVIRONMENTAL DATA PROJECT

OPPORTUNITY BRIEF

*Collaborative environmental data stewardship:
Opportunities for ecosystem building
and project application*

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The collection and use of environmental data is proliferating, supporting communities, researchers, and governments to solve environmental and climate crises on local and global scales. With data coming from disparate sources and actors, collaborative tools are increasingly necessary - especially if we're to responsibly account for and integrate the complex and intersectional nature of environmental issues. Environmental data users, collectors, and owners can practice responsible data stewardship in collaboration with others in new and profound ways in order to leverage the power of expanding data resources.

Open Environmental Data Project convened stakeholders from government, academia, environmental nonprofits, community organizations, and the legal sector to discuss the challenges and promising solutions they've faced in collaboratively managing and stewarding environmental data. Different needs and opportunities emerged based on the actor's role in the collaboratively managed data space; we categorize the opportunities as either ecosystem-building opportunities, based on their application towards building the larger environmental data space, or as project application opportunities, opportunities for environmental data stewardship in practice or applied to specific collaborative environmental data projects. This brief focuses on the following thirteen opportunities on both the ecosystem- building and project application levels:

1. Intermediary organizations can create and host a data resource library for data users, stewards, and collectors that can support project development with policy and technical documents.
2. Intermediary organizations can explore applications of an environmental data tagging framework as a way to protect sensitive community data while ensuring representation.
3. Project stewardship teams can create contractual terms of use, providing a sense of security and commonality among stewards.
4. Project stewardship teams can collectively determine the metadata standards that accompany dataset inputs to increase interoperability and further collaboration among users and collectors.
5. Intermediary organizations can foster a cross-disciplinary collective of data specialists to support community collaborative environmental data projects.
6. Project stewardship teams can create a community stewardship team of data stewards, users, and collectors at the onset of the project to enable other project-application opportunities in this brief.
7. Intermediary organizations can create standardized data sharing templates and share guidance, creating an incentive for the private sector to open up their data.
8. Project stewardship teams can research and set up a data trust to place their data or data rights under the control of a trustee, or board of trustees, and secure legal protections.
9. Intermediary organizations can research and utilize new types of licenses to protect Indigenous data and enable Indigenous communities to retain data and intellectual property within Western data constructs.
10. Intermediary organizations can research additional instances where data protections are necessary, and explore the needs of different communities, what governance and technical tools could be created, and what kind of policy or legal mechanisms could have an impact.

11. Project stewardship teams have the opportunity to partner with organizations that are researching and developing Indigenous data sovereignty software, use Indigenous-built software, and recognize the specific data storage technologies that could host and protect Indigenous data.
12. Intermediary organizations can work to accelerate state and federal agencies' ability to address capacity needs surrounding integration of collaborative models.
13. Project stewardship teams can establish a partnership with a government data champion to increase positive governance feedback cycles.

While this field is nascent, it is rife with potential. With support from intermediary organizations and continued collaborative experimentation from project stewardship teams, new technical, social, and governance innovations can materialize regarding the stewardship of environmental data, all in service of solving our most urgent environmental and climate emergencies.

COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENTAL DATA STEWARDSHIP: INTRODUCTION

We face more dire environmental and climate crises than ever before. We also have more access to sources of environmental data than ever before with large-scale environmental datasets increasingly being opened up for public use (e.g., [NASA](#) and the [UN Biodiversity Lab](#)) and expanding numbers of community monitoring networks being established. Our collective ability to use environmental data to solve urgent crises relies on our capacity to collaboratively steward this data. Data is critical for creating evidence from the local to the global, and allows for both small- and large-scale decision-makers to have a more responsive understanding of their changing environment. With data coming from disparate sources and actors, collaborative tools are increasingly necessary - especially if we're to responsibly account for and integrate the complex and intersectional nature of environmental issues. Collaborative data processes are essential in that they also underscore cooperative organization, often including co-creation of tools that prioritize community needs, while modeling more democratic engagement between communities, researchers, governments, and the data they use. Effective environmental data stewardship relies on the ability of multiple parties with varied goals to work together to reap the benefits of robust data sources.

Across sectors, additional interest and attention is dedicated to the role of environmental data stewardship. In the US, collaborative environmental data initiatives like the [Internet of Water](#) are receiving transformative investment from the [Infrastructure Investment and Jobs Act](#). New models of data collaboration are being developed to handle the nuance of different environmental data, and the needs of stakeholders and stewards using this data, e.g., the [California Data Collaborative](#)'s work building a foundation for water utility data sharing.¹ This is an opportune moment to look at what is working, what has the potential to adapt and scale, and what can happen in the coming years to galvanize environmental data collaboration.

Collaborative environmental data projects can unlock the potential of data that was previously siloed, difficult to use, or inaccessible. These projects can provide the technical and legal structures needed to open previously proprietary data and data that requires additional privacy. Additionally, as we'll explore in this brief, we are witnessing how technical and legal systems are beginning to accommodate collaborative environmental data projects. Effective projects can set up governance systems that respond to the users' priorities and incentives to participate in a responsive manner. Collaborative environmental data projects can legitimate data users and their data in a way that makes it easier to create evidence and advocate for themselves. Ultimately, collaborative structures give more power to the people collecting and using data.

This is a guide to the possibilities in the collaborative environmental data space, with a focus on community priorities, not a discussion of the myriad different types of collaborative data governance models.² In this brief, we categorize the opportunities as either **ecosystem-building opportunities**, based on their application towards building the larger environmental data space (see Figure 1 on next page), or as **project application opportunities**, opportunities for environmental data stewardship in practice or applied to specific collaborative environmental data projects (see Figure 2).

¹ See OEDP's Anatomy of Environmental Decision Making blog post, written by Christopher Tull on the California Data Collaborative's work on water utility data sharing, [here](#).

² We recommend looking to places such as Aapti Institute's Data Economy Lab for resources on collaborative governance models. There are many great resources that document the different types of collaborative governance models, including Aapti Institute's [Data Economy Lab](#) and [Understanding Data Stewardship report](#).

ECOSYSTEM BUILDING OPPORTUNITIES

Figure 1: Ecosystem building opportunities. The circle graphic displays the ecosystem-building opportunities explored in this brief.

PROJECT APPLICATION OPPORTUNITIES

Figure 2: Project application opportunities. The data lifecycle process shown with the project application opportunities explored in this brief mapped upon it.

COMMONLY USED TERMS

Data intermediary organization:

Organizations that fall within this categorization are the main audience for our ecosystem-building opportunities and include non-profit organizations, academic research institutions, community organizations who are working on issues related to environmental and climate data, open data, sharing, and governance. They usually do not store data themselves, but instead research, build capacity, and support data stewards in using data and communicating with other stakeholders.

Collaborative environmental data project:

A collaborative environmental data project includes both technical and non-technical components. Technical aspects may include any of the common data stewardship models that includes a digital interface or platform, e.g. data collaboratives, data exchanges, data trusts, sharing platforms, data commons, or personal data stores. Non-technical aspects include the cooperative processes that surround the creation or maintenance of a digital model and the collection and use of data. A project might be initiated by an academic institution, a government agency, an NGO, a data intermediary, or any combination of stakeholders.

Data steward:

A data steward is often an intermediary that facilitates or holds consent and decision-making power on behalf of its users, and is responsible for maintaining security and quality of datasets (Manohar et al, 2020). A steward of data can decide who has access, under what conditions, and to whose benefit (Mills, 2019).

Data stewardship:

Stewardship can vary based on context, but we are specifically considering data stewardship in this brief, which denotes the roles and responsibilities of a data steward, or the sustainable and responsible management of data for public benefit (Verhulst et al, 2020).

Environmental data:

When this brief refers to “environmental data,” we encapsulate climate data into that signifier. Environmental and climate data can take many forms—air, water, or soil quality data sets; weather data; population data; satellite imagery; photography; art; descriptions of lived experiences and histories. We also consider health data that is related to environmental impacts, but recognize that the regulations are much more stringent due to the data’s sensitivity. In reimagining the social use of data, we place equal importance on qualitative and quantitative data.

Interoperability:

The FAIR Guiding Principles define interoperability as “the ability of data or tools from non-cooperating resources to integrate or work together with minimal effort” (Wilkinson et al., 2016). In general, this means that data from different sources (as well as their metadata) use standardized, compatible, or easily translatable formats, structures, and vocabularies.

A NOTE ON METHODOLOGY

We base the discussion and recommendations in this brief on insights from a Brain Trust held in September 2022, which brought together twelve participants from academia, data initiatives, and government. We discussed the challenges surrounding collaborative environmental data stewardship, as well as models and approaches that have been successful, and the possibilities for the future within this space. The participants are quoted throughout this brief, and names and affiliations are listed on pg. 24.

INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES

When environmental data stewardship is successful, communities participating in data stewardship have more control and ownership of their data, and decision-makers have a more holistic picture of an issue, making it easier to make decisions that address root causes and community impact. For example, [integrating PFAS sampling data](#) from regulatory agencies, academics, NGOs and environmental organizations in North Carolina led to a clearer understanding of the correlation between drinking water safety and contamination sources. This resulted in more attention from city governments to fund filtration and increased sampling of affected areas. This points to the significance of a robust environmental data ecosystem in fostering collaborative projects to address the environmental and climate issues of our time. Successful environmental data stewardship expands the leverage of community data to influence policy and opens doors for increased democratic participation based on evidence. In turn, this highlights community priorities and strengthens avenues of civic participation and input.

This brief is organized by five key insights compiled from our Brain Trust and subsequent research: A) develop a common language and glossary, B) create and sustain multiple modes of participation, C) utilize legal mechanisms, D) prioritize data protection through ethical design, and E) embrace a polycentric approach.

Ecosystem
Building
Opportunity

Ecosystem-building opportunities point to work that can be picked up by data intermediary organizations in order to foster greater environmental data stewardship, aiding individual projects in a collective manner by increasing capacity and recognizing critical needs and gaps in support.

Project
Application
Opportunity

Project application opportunities are presented for data collectors, users, and stewards to consider when designing or forming a collaborative environmental data project. Many of the opportunities are useful at the onset of the project, while others are meant to be considered in the maintenance and management of the project.

A. DEVELOP A COMMON LANGUAGE & GLOSSARY

THE **INSIGHT**

In forming collaborative environmental data projects, there are many roles to fill, and many forms of expertise and experience needed to ensure successful collaboration. When starting a collaborative environmental data model with community data, Anna Berti Suman, Principal Investigator of the project Sensing for Justice (Sensjus), noted the need to develop a common language among disparate cultures and practitioners, and even among people in the same community. She stated it can be helpful to have a process in which you create a common glossary based on group understanding and consensus, rather than top-down definitions. Stacy Timmons, Associate Director for Hydrology Programs at the New Mexico Bureau of Geology and Mineral Resources, echoed this need, commenting, “when I say data, I’m literally thinking of tables of data, but there are other people who think of something else entirely and really, there are so many terms and so many points of potential misunderstanding.” Collaborative projects have a wide spectrum of users: bringing together data users, government representatives, and technical or legal advisors with the goal of moving forward *with one another* in the project is critical for success.

THE **OPPORTUNITIES**

Working toward a “common glossary” presents opportunities for cooperation and pre-project partnership development and grounds shared understandings before any legal statements come into conversation. There are ecosystem-building opportunities that will increase understanding, and project application opportunities that address legal and technical aspects of data stewardship, and ultimately, strengthen the relationships and set the foundation for partnership and future governance discussions.

Ecosystem
Building
Opportunity

1. CREATE AND HOST A DATA RESOURCE LIBRARY FOR DATA USERS, STEWARDS, AND COLLECTORS

There’s an opportunity for an intermediary organization to create a data resource library that could be adapted and used by collaborative data projects. Examples of resources could include: guidance on FAIR³ and CARE⁴ principles and practices, the policy landscape of the stored data, data sharing agreement templates, templates for crafting evidence-based policy memos, funding opportunities, and an archive of current and past sectoral partnerships. A resource library could be collaboratively managed and contributed to, and a culture of collective maintenance is necessary for addressing the rapidly shifting nature of environmental data policy and technology.

³ FAIR principles are Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets. They assist in machine-actionability, or the capacity of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with none or minimal human intervention. For more on FAIR principles, see [here](#).

⁴ CARE principles are complementary to the FAIR principles and reflect the crucial role of data in advancing Indigenous innovation and self-determination. CARE is an acronym that stands for Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics. For more on CARE principles, see [here](#).

INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES

[The Internet of Water Coalition's Learning Center](#) is an excellent example of a resource library, available for anyone working in water data, but especially for the data hubs and initiatives affiliated with their hub and peer networks. The Learning Center includes examples of legislation and policy reports, past technical presentations, how-tos and guidance documents, and [Data Stories](#) (article-style examples of how water data led to better outcomes, submitted by their peer network).

In the design of a collaborative environmental data project platform, collaborative initiatives can embed this resource library in their own sites alongside datasets. At the onset of a project, data stewards can determine what would be additionally beneficial to include. They can then work to create, gather, and add those resources. This process can be incredibly useful for group cohesion and capacity building.

Ecosystem
Building
Opportunity

2. EXPLORE APPLICATIONS OF AN ENVIRONMENTAL DATA TAGGING FRAMEWORK

There's an opportunity for data intermediaries to explore the application of an environmental data tagging framework that could ensure ultimate control rests with the person or community providing the data and can be used in the case of sensitive community data, where only specific users could have access at predetermined times. An environmental data tagging framework would allow a collaborative environmental data project team to conduct a dialogue on how stakeholders' values and principles should be expressed. An established metadata manager can facilitate a series of conversations at the onset of a project to help stewards determine the significant tags that indicate boundaries of where, how, and with whom data can be shared.

For example, a collaborative environmental data project that focuses on forest data might want to engage certain protections on economic valuation data that would be suitable to share for research, but not for commercial purposes. Stewards could apply a tag to the data (e.g., "Research purposes only"), and users would have to verify their affiliation with a university before accessing the data.

When working with Indigenous communities and data in particular, [Local Contexts'](#) development of TK (Traditional Knowledge) and BC (Biocultural) labels allow communities to express specific local conditions for sharing and engaging in future research and relationships in ways that are consistent with existing community rules, governance, and protocols for using, sharing, and circulating knowledge and data. The labels are customized by each community, supporting the "inclusion of local protocols for access and use to cultural heritage that is digitally circulating outside community contexts" (Local Contexts, 2022). The TK and BC labels can offer lessons for data collection and management in communities who have experienced extractive data practices; for instance, a tagging system for environmental data could be used in the case of sensitive community data within an environmental justice setting, where only specific users could have access at predetermined times.

Project
Application
Opportunity

3. CREATE A CONTRACTUAL TERMS OF USE

At the beginning of any collaborative environmental data initiative, there is an opportunity for potential users and contributors to create a contractual terms of use: a set of legal terms that govern what can and cannot be done with their data, creating obligations between the operator of a project and users of the data (Porcaro, 2019). A terms of use would vary based on the stewards' needs and project type, but could include information about:

- Ownership rights over data collected
- Data analysis possibilities
- Options and benefits for "opting-in" to other data related opportunities (e.g. environmental assessments)
- Terms that include provisions to secure and protect data, and utilize industry best practices privacy and confidentiality
- Stewards' rights on choosing to delete their submitted data (Porcaro, 2019)

Collaboratively determining a terms of use contract can provide a sense of security and commonality among data collectors, users, and stewards. Reviewing these contracts on an agreed upon basis can allow for adaptation and revision; this is critical for environmental data projects in that rapid circumstantial shifts due to climate change are now the norm and may influence a steward's priorities and risks.

Project
Application
Opportunity

4. COLLECTIVELY DETERMINE THE METADATA STANDARDS THAT ACCOMPANY DATASET INPUTS

At the onset of the creation of a collaborative environmental data initiative, there is an opportunity for the community of data stewards and users to come together and determine the metadata structure that accompany the dataset inputs. A community of data stewards can apply the metadata standards relevant to the project, e.g. [EPA Metadata Style Guide](#), [UKEOF](#), [Common Information Model](#), [Ecological Metadata Language](#), [Climate and Forecast Metadata Convention](#), etc. Metadata is a type of common glossary that allows for greater interoperability with outside datasets, allows for machine readability, and sets a standard for future data collection efforts within the project.

INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES

B. CREATE & SUSTAIN MULTIPLE MODES OF PARTICIPATION

THE **INSIGHT**

Data management and stewardship, especially in environmental data collaborative spaces, must prioritize social and governance considerations in addition to technical aspects of the approach. An oft-repeated sentiment in the Brain Trust was that multiple modes of participation throughout the data lifecycle are essential to ensuring representative decision-making, and the technical aspects of any project must reflect community priorities and provide tools for continued community decision-making. Stacy Timmons spoke to this point, adding: "There's everything from the data collector in the field to the decision maker at the other end, who need to do something with the data and each person cares about different things. They just want to know that this [process] is to be trusted, and this is okay. There are so many different places that people can be on that spectrum of understanding [the data and its lifecycle] that it's really important to figure out how to communicate all through that spectrum."

Creating different modes of participation points recognizes that different data stewards and users have different motivations, needs, and challenges. Deborah Tien, co-founder of Common Agency, pointed out: "I think when many of us talk about 'community,' we treat 'community'... like it's some sort of monolith, but within communities it's quite diverse and heterogeneous - and power can vary." Climate change and environmental pollution emergencies affect communities in different and intersectional ways, and these impacts often influence why and how individuals are interested in a collaborative data project. Understanding these impacts, needs, and motivations, along with the specific characteristics and the nuanced set of relationships within a community, can enable meaningful participation and representation.

THE **OPPORTUNITIES**

There is a broad opportunity within all collaborative environmental data projects for the community to be involved at all points of the data lifecycle. Recognizing the entry points and modes for community participation early on, as well as revisiting them throughout the project, can address the disparate needs, motivations, and priorities of the community.

5. FOSTER A CROSS-DISCIPLINARY COLLECTIVE OF DATA SPECIALISTS

Collaborative environmental data projects require different types of expertise throughout the lifecycle of the data and the projects, including experts on data subject matter, community sociocultural history experts, policy and legal advisors, and technical consultants. Currently, there are few resources available to collaborative environmental data projects when questions arise about legal or technical aspects. A data intermediary organization could play a role in creating a collective of interested specialists who are interested in connecting with individual projects to increase capacity at different points throughout the project, as requested by a stewardship team.

Ecosystem
Building
Opportunity

Project
Application
Opportunity

6. CREATE A TEAM OF DATA STEWARDS, USERS, AND COLLECTORS

At the onset of any collaborative environmental data project, it is critical to recognize the varied roles needed throughout the lifecycle of the data. The specialist roles listed in the previous opportunity will be useful at certain points, while the community members interested in data collection and use will be strategic in conducting outreach, providing input, and connecting with local government as constituents. Creating a stewardship team of diverse community members with representatives in each of these various roles will allow for other opportunities in this brief to be possible; the stewardship team can determine legal and technical needs, plan and participate in metadata creation and curation, be in conversation with local decision makers, when applicable determine the use of labels (i.e., those from Local Contexts), and support in determining the project's needs and assets. Each of these roles requires a different level of participation and input dependent on the capabilities of the individual(s) and allows for a greater number of the community to be involved and build value.⁵ Environmental issues are rarely siloed and require diverse data sources, but also diverse degrees of community input and involvement for solution-building.

⁵ For more on who to involve when developing participatory data mechanisms, see [Participatory data stewardship](#), a report published by the Ada Lovelace Institute.

C. UTILIZE INNOVATIVE LEGAL MECHANISMS

THE **INSIGHT**

Environmental data can often be personal and laden with risks and liabilities. For example, data on lead pipes or flood risk with someone's home could decrease home values or raise insurance prices. Environmental data can also often be guarded or proprietary due to its commercial value, as with offshore seafloor data collected by offshore wind companies. In both cases, the data may be valuable to both stewards and decision makers, but there are rarely incentives to share without legal protection in place. Legal mechanisms can cater to more collaborative data sharing setups to create incentives for better data stewardship and offering protection for the stewards themselves. Annie Brett, Assistant Professor of Law at the University of Florida, pointed to the need for better data governance structures that can utilize legal mechanisms and manage a large variety of data and privacy concerns. Brett commented, "on the technical side, we just need more resources to be able to structure, protect, and access data better, and we also need more resources to be able to answer the legal questions of which there are many, and unfortunately very different for different types of data."

THE **OPPORTUNITIES**

There is no one-size-fits-all legal mechanism for creating incentives or providing protection in the case of environmental data collaborative structures. Each set of legal mechanisms must cater to the particular geography, sector, issue at hand. Creating standardized data sharing templates and building data trusts are two opportunities that can be adapted based on a project's unique needs and barriers.

7. CREATE STANDARDIZED DATA SHARING TEMPLATES AND SHARE GUIDANCE

Creating standardized data sharing templates can in turn create an incentive to open up and share data held by the private sector -- data that might be useful for other organizations, the public sector, or communities. Annie Brett, who works with offshore wind and seafloor data, also noted the need to create incentives, like standardized data sharing templates, saying: "[Offshore wind companies would] be willing to share the data. But they don't want to go through the hassle of figuring out what the restrictions on sharing are and what the legal considerations need to be to create these data usage sharing agreements. As part of this project, we are thinking about standardized use agreements that would make it much simpler for companies to overcome their knee jerk reaction, which is, 'Oh no, we can't share that because workers will freak out.'"

INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES

The [NERRS Science Collaborative](#) provided a template that could be adapted based on context,⁶ but essentially include:

- A general description of the data to be managed: temporal and geographic coverage of the data, data types captured or created, how data will be collected, and whether data will contain personally identifiable information
- Data quality control and quality assurance procedures: procedures employed and the plan for the overall life cycle of the data
- Data documentation and metadata standards: what standards will be used to represent data and metadata elements in this collection
- Data access and sharing: how and if the data will be available to the public, holds or delays between collection and publication, data access protocols, conditions, or restrictions
- Data archive: where and how the data will be stored, protected, and what processes to follow in the event of unauthorized access

Working through answering and documenting these questions in collaborative settings protects both public and private data users, minimizes risk, and enables stewards to de-identify any personal information. Standardized environmental data sharing templates can be created by researchers, intermediary organizations, or government agencies for broader use, adoption, and adaptation for local data projects. The [Contracts for Data Collaboration](#) has a framework organized around 6 categories of questions that naturally emerge in data steward and user conversations and include questions like: *why is the data being shared?* or *what kinds of data are being shared?* or *who is party to the agreement?*, among others. This framework could provide a template for specific sectors or geographies to take and adapt. As it stands today, data sharing agreements are created on a project-by-project basis, but there is an opportunity for data intermediary organizations to create sector-based templates and provide guidance to the broader community.

8. SET UP A DATA TRUST

Data trusts, as a legal mechanism, present an opportunity for a community starting a collaborative environmental data project to place their data or data rights under the control of a trustee, or board of trustees. “The trustees have a fiduciary duty to look after the sole interest of the beneficiaries,” (Ruhaak, 2020) i.e., the data users with a stake in preventing their data being abused. Within an environmental data setting, this might mean the protection of individual fishermen whose vessel collects geographic information on each trip or of homeowners who hold sensitive data regarding the lead pipes in their home. Data trusts are relevant when there is an asset or right that can be handed over to a board of trustees, such as land, water, or access rights. Establishing a data trust allows for the data trustees’ and users’ responsibilities to be legally defined and allocated, and ensures that a clear set of rules, principles, and guidelines determine data access and use. Data trusts allow for sensitive information to be protected in a legally determined manner.

A document called the “terms of powers” outlines what the board is specifically allowed to do with the data (Porcaro, 2019). Trustees, or data managers, should be established within a local collaborative data project, and data collectors and users should be given the opportunity to participate in determining sharing agreement terms. Porcaro (2019) lists examples of what abilities a board of trustees might have in the context of a fisheries alliance, including providing individual fishermen their own data and video on request, verifying data from official sources, providing data to parties who have access to it, and

⁶ For an example of the NERRS Science Collaborative’s Data Sharing Plan, see [here](#).

INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES

managing data licenses. The independence of trustees is essential in that they represent the data users and stewards fairly, representing as wide a range of interests as possible.

Data trusts can allow for varying levels of participation—key for environmental data collaborative models where some users or stewards may be more active or passive in participation and hold varying roles. They can adopt various technical models, ranging from centralized models where data subjects share their data with the trustee or decentralized models where users or data controllers hold the data, but the rights and decision-making powers over this data are assigned to the trust (Data Economy Lab, 2022).

Data trusts for environmental data are still largely undefined and have not been widely adopted. Organizations like [PLACE](#) are documenting their process of design, noting the numerous barriers they've faced in establishing a data trust for location data. PLACE notes that since a data collaboration of this nature has not been set up before, there is no blueprint to follow, especially in niche sectors. Additionally, they note the need to structure their governance model around “the right incentives to ensure we are held accountable for our actions and decision making while not losing our ability to be agile and financially sustainable” (Rabley & Keefe, 2021). Brain Trust participant Suha Mohamed, Strategy and Partnerships Lead at the Aapti Institute, pointed out [research from Aapti Institute and the Open Data Institute](#) that global legal landscapes are often unable to facilitate data trusts as a bottom-up means of governance and that there are still many avenues to explore and expand on concerning operational functioning and strategy. Groups aiming to build collaborative environmental data governance systems will likely face similar barriers, indicating the opportunity for intermediaries in the environmental data and data space more broadly to support data trust pilots with operational and funding support.

INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES

D. PRIORITIZE DATA PROTECTION THROUGH ETHICAL DESIGN

THE **INSIGHT**

Environmental data stewards must balance the needs unique to communities holding sensitive data with those for accessibility to ensure representation in the collaboration model's design. Collaborative approaches that host both Indigenous data⁷ and knowledge and non-Indigenous data must recognize the rights inherent to Indigenous data stewards, environmental and climate justice communities and users, and adhere to CARE and OCAP principles. OCAP is an acronym that stands for Ownership, Control, Access, Possession and asserts that First Nations alone have control over data collection processes in their communities, and that they own and control how this information can be stored, interpreted, used, or shared. Critically applying the practices related to CARE and OCAP principles is one of the first steps toward Indigenous data sovereignty and data protection for vulnerable communities .

Collaborative projects that include data from environmental or climate justice communities also require CARE principle application, as the framework is relevant for any data representing individuals and communities who have experienced extractive practices with little or no benefit returned (Carroll et al, 2021, p. 3). Environmental and climate justice communities have specific data needs that will only become more salient as the climate crisis intensifies, and ethics surrounding the ways in which data represents communities

Stewards must consider sharing and privacy controls, technical features, and the organizational structure to secure community ownership and control of data while ensuring that the data can be used collaboratively to answer community driven research questions. Brain Trust participant Suha Mohamed noted: "I think there's an interesting perspective in having communities also decide if they don't want to share data, [...] if data falls into the wrong hands, the linking of data can be even more damaging, and can open up other sets of information than can lead to surveillance or targeting." To reduce harm while ensuring representation, collaborative projects can operationalize situated openness, offering different modes of sharing and protections.

THE **OPPORTUNITIES**

These opportunities are recommended for project stewardship teams and intermediary organizations that wish to create and support a data collaborative model that can protect both Indigenous and non-Indigenous data while addressing cross-boundary environmental and climate issues.

⁷ Indigenous data is defined here as data in a wide variety of formats inclusive of digital data and data as knowledge and information. It encompasses data, information, and knowledge about Indigenous individuals, collectives, entities, lifeways, cultures, lands, and resources (Rainie et al, 2019).

INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES

Ecosystem
Building
Opportunity

9. RESEARCH AND USE ALTERNATIVE TYPES OF LICENSES TO PROTECT INDIGENOUS DATA

There is an opportunity to research and utilize new types of licenses to protect Indigenous data that recognizes the need for new types of community stewardship of data and in turn, provides ways for communities to interact and share data within non-Western frameworks.

The [Kaitiakitanga license](#), for example, was developed by the Māori people to protect data in repositories and provide access as seen fit through their tikanga (Māori customs and protocols). Based on the Māori word Kaitiaki, Kaitiakitanga is akin to guardianship, protectorship (Te Hiku Media, 2022). The guidelines for usage include: “that each kaitiaki may make data available for download as deemed suitable by the tikanga associated with that data, and users may download data to their devices via the [Whare Kōrero app](#), but the kaitiakitanga remains with the kaitiaki, and by downloading the data to your device, unless you have kaitiaki rights to the data, users agree: a. not to extract the data from the app; and b. only access the data through the app” (Te Hiku, 2022).⁸ The development of this type of license presents a model for others that enable Indigenous communities to retain data and intellectual property within Western data constructs.

The Łíídlıı Kúé First Nation (LKFN) has partnered with the Scotty Creek Research Station to develop a similar kind of license, but specifically for research purposes. Along with other safeguards, the [research license application](#) also secures agreements from outside researchers that “all raw data collected in this project will be shared with the Łíídlıı Kúé First Nation at the end of each project year. As such, Łíídlıı Kúé First Nation will be co-owners of these data.” The LKFN developed this license as a way to more immediately connect the researchers to the community and the land itself, and recognize community needs (Pilkington, 2022). Research licenses like this one could be adapted and integrated into environmental data collaborative projects when Indigenous datasets and traditional knowledge is joined in with non-Indigenous data, allowing for stewards to engage in a deeper level of responsibility and accountability.

The creation of appropriate licenses and software could prove critical as more environmental data is collected in Indigenous communities to support decision making across the gamut of topics, including directing land use and water management decisions to determining relocation of communities threatened by climate change (Flavelle, 2022). The data needed to make these decisions about funding allocation includes environmental and demographic data, and collaborative environmental data projects may have a role to play in more standardized collection and responsible management of sensitive data. Being able to synthesize different sources of data, i.e., satellite images or data generated from mobile phone users before and after a disaster, in one centralized interface could allow for more deliberate analysis and better informed decision-making.

⁸ The repository for the development of the Kaitiakitanga License is available on [Github](#).

INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES

Ecosystem
Building
Opportunity

10. RESEARCH ADDITIONAL INSTANCES WHERE DATA PROTECTIONS ARE NECESSARY

The increasing datafication of our personal lives and the increasing urgency of the climate crisis and multiple pollution emergencies are compounding the need for more data protections, especially in the instance of community-generated or owned data. There's a gap in research on what protections will be needed with non-Indigenous communities, especially in environmental and climate justice communities. Intermediary data organizations and researchers have the opportunity to explore the needs of different communities, what governance and technical tools could be created, and what kind of policy or legal mechanisms could have impact.

Project
Application
Opportunity

11. PARTNER WITH INDIGENOUS ORGANIZATIONS WHO ARE RESEARCHING AND DEVELOPING DATA SOVEREIGNTY SOFTWARE

Project stewardship teams have the opportunity to partner with organizations that are researching and developing Indigenous data sovereignty software, use Indigenous-built software, and recognize the specific data storage technologies that could host and protect Indigenous data. [Animikii](#), for example, is an Indigenous-owned technology company that provides website design and custom software services, recognizing that custom software is often cost-prohibitive, and that non-customizable software options rarely allow for the unique technical needs of Indigenous data storage. Building on this work, an Indigenous Data Sovereignty data software template could be useful and would “need to be both replicable enough to benefit from economies of scale and modular enough to account for sometimes paradoxical, community-defined data” (Animikii, 2020). A feature of this data software could be decentralized end-to-end encrypted storage tools like [Tahoe-LAFS](#), that could allow “organizations to host their data within the organization as well as have off-site backups without having to worry about the data being accessed by third parties without permission” (Animikii, 2020). Animikii are at the forefront of Indigenous innovation, and still in development of their web-based software, called [Niiwin](#), that empowers Indigenous data sovereignty. This is particularly relevant for projects where Indigenous data may be shared and stored alongside non-Indigenous data, and companies like Animikii can provide projects with software that fits the needs of all data stewards, while allowing for ensured representation and collaboration with and between stewards.

E. EMBRACE A POLYCENTRIC APPROACH

THE *INSIGHT*

While Brain Trust participants could easily point to small-scale, local projects that feature successful models of environmental data stewardship, they often noted the need for the capacity to scale and ability to integrate into different levels of government for greater impact. Luis Felipe Murrillo, Faculty Fellow at the Notre Dame Technology Ethics Center, specifically noted how “robust polycentricity” could enable data governance to happen “on many levels—local, regional—where people are able to come up with local solutions for managing and caring for the data that are really adjusted to local needs. If you give a lot of autonomy to local initiatives, they can self-organize, and be nested into each other, with the ability to scale up to address bigger issues.” This is especially significant with environmental and climate issues which are inherently intersectional and interconnected, as Luis Felipe pointed out: “It is important to figure out micro-level things related to the environment, but we need solutions that are much bigger, right? We need environmental and climate solutions at a continental scale, a planetary scale, and we can’t get there without a nesting structure for projects to scale up.”

This builds on ideas from Elinor and Vincent Ostrom’s research on polycentricity in self-organized groups for managing common natural resources, which posits that the optimum scale of production is not the same for all urban public goods and services, there are a multiplicity of decision makers and centers of power that naturally have systems providing incentives leading to self-organized, self-corrective institutional change (Ostrom et al, 1961). A polycentric approach to environmental data collaborative projects would rely on what Ostrom calls spontaneity, or “patterns of organization within a polycentric system will be self-generating or self-organizing in the sense that individuals acting at all levels will have the incentives to create or institute appropriate patterns of ordered relationships” and depend on the value and culture of the individuals creating them (Aligica & Tarko, 2012, p. 246). While the two following opportunities are explicitly related to this theory, all of the opportunities listed in this brief include some aspects of the polycentric approach and benefit from its framing. Several Brain Trust participants agreed that more examples of this concept of polycentricity and scaling working in practice are needed within the scope of collaborative environmental data projects.

THE *OPPORTUNITIES*

Building local collaborative structures that can feed into larger regulatory mandates can help address local issues more effectively and inform broader policy decisions. The following two opportunities address different aspects of building a “bottom-up” approach to collaborative environmental data models that can be scaled, integrated, and nested.

Ecosystem
Building
Opportunity

12. ACCELERATE STATE AND FEDERAL AGENCIES' ABILITY TO ADDRESS CAPACITY NEEDS SURROUNDING INTEGRATION OF COLLABORATIVE MODELS

Federal and state agencies can support local and other bottom-up efforts in integrating well with each other, and within federated systems. For example, as Brain Trust participant Shelby Switzer, Fellow at the Georgetown University Beeck Center, added: "There's a big opportunity for the federal government to play a role in some of the standards setting, at least providing that convening space for people to come together and create and agree to the standards, and also providing capacity to help actually implement the standards." In a previous opportunity brief "[Look to the Local](#)," we pointed to opportunities for state governments to do standard-setting through adopting Master Data Sharing Agreements, collaboratively designed with communities and other stakeholder groups, to set data management standards and establish processes for safely sharing fine-grained and de-identified datasets with the public. This form of standardization and focus on data policy encourages a culture of sharing by creating a presumption of openness among agencies and creates incentives for more agencies to share and use more community data. Standards-setting would assist in the interoperability and integration of datasets and collaborative models, effectively making scaling possible. This opportunity would be most effective if alongside setting standards and holding convenings, federal and state agencies increased capacity building funding for locally based environmental data collaborative approaches.

Project
Application
Opportunity

13. ESTABLISH A PARTNERSHIP WITH A GOVERNMENT DATA CHAMPION

Local environmental data stewards prosper with the autonomy to make governance decisions that highlight their priorities, but would also benefit from established relationships with a data champion in government that is one "step up" the governance scale. We consider data champions in government as civil servants who have interest and work with specific datasets and data management, have sectorally relevant knowledge related to data or environmental governance, or have an interest in data driven evidence-based policy making. Places to look might include state Offices of Innovation, the offices of Chief Data Officers at the state and city level, state and local environmental resource boards. Government data champions can aid a collaborative environmental data project in two ways: 1) by connecting project teams with useful open datasets and aiding in questions of interoperability and sharing, and 2) by informing project teams of upcoming and relevant policy discussions or votes where the data could be used as evidence or outcomes could affect project goals, e.g., an local agency staffer could alert their local water data collaborative about upcoming proposed legislation related to stormwater or flooding or assist them in preparing data for a public comment period.

An opportunity for data stewards looking to establish a collaborative environmental data project, is to conduct outreach with local government to find at least one staffer with an interest in environmental data issues or tech, or in data more generally, and incorporate them into the project as an advisor. For example, a citywide collaborative initiative working with air quality data in North Carolina would benefit from a relationship with a data specialist from the North Carolina State Climate Office from the onset of the project. Project teams should look to the different offices outside of political offices, to the civil servants in various agencies, and consider what type of role would make a good partner for their project. Data champions who have an understanding of the state or regional data landscape can be instrumental in making connections between local projects and generally understanding the processual pipeline that information flows through, from community collection to decision-making moments.

CONCLUSION

Environmental data stewardship presents unique challenges that require unique solutions. The opportunities presented in this brief point to distinct leverage points that stewards can utilize in their creation of collaborative environmental data projects or in their support of the broader environmental data ecosystem. The topic of collaborative environmental data is nascent, with new tools and approaches developing rapidly, and a goal of this brief is to inspire and highlight additional areas for data stewards, users, and intermediaries to explore through research and practice. The considerations within individual projects and the broader ecosystem are complex, with technical, governance, and legal cogs that must work in tandem.

This brief laid out several opportunities to address these considerations at both a project and ecosystem level:

1. **Intermediary organizations can create and host a data resource library for data users, stewards, and collectors** that can support project development with policy and technical documents.
2. **Intermediary organizations can explore applications of an environmental data tagging framework** as a way to protect sensitive community data while ensuring representation.
3. **Project stewardship teams can create contractual terms of use**, providing a sense of security and commonality among stewards.
4. **Project stewardship teams can collectively determine the metadata standards that accompany dataset inputs** to increase interoperability and further collaboration among users and collectors.
5. **Intermediary organizations can foster a cross-disciplinary collective of data specialists** to support community collaborative environmental data projects.
6. **Project stewardship teams can create a community stewardship team of data stewards, users, and collectors** at the onset of the project to enable other project-application opportunities in this brief.
7. **Intermediary organizations can create standardized data sharing templates and share guidance**, creating an incentive for the private sector to open up their data.
8. **Project stewardship teams can research and set up a data trust** to place their data or data rights under the control of a trustee, or board of trustees, and secure legal protections.
9. **Intermediary organizations can research and use new types of licenses** to protect Indigenous data and enable Indigenous communities to retain data and intellectual property within Western data constructs.
10. **Intermediary organizations can research additional instances where data protections are necessary**, and explore the needs of different communities, what governance and technical tools could be created, and what kind of policy or legal mechanisms could have an impact.
11. **Project stewardship teams have the opportunity to partner with organizations that are researching and developing Indigenous data sovereignty software**, use Indigenous-built software, and recognize the specific data storage technologies that could host and protect Indigenous data.
12. **Intermediary organizations can work to accelerate state and federal agencies' ability to address capacity needs** surrounding integration of collaborative models.
13. **Project stewardship teams can establish a partnership with a government data champion** to increase positive governance feedback cycles.

Through project application and ecosystem-building, there are entry points for government staff, community leaders and organizations, technologists, designers, legal experts, and academics to steward environmental data and support the infrastructures for environmental data stewardship. While the considerations are complex, participation in the opportunities surrounding collaborative environmental data stewardship is crucial to our collective ability to solve environmental and climate emergencies.

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